

Studies on the kinetics of tetrahexylammonium bromochromate oxidation of methionine in various percentage of acetic acid + *N,N*-dimethylformamide mixture

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Abstract : Methionine (Met) is a naturally occurring sulphur containing amino acid. The kinetics of oxidation of methionine by tetrahexylammonium bromochromate (THexABC) in various percentage of acetic acid + *N,N*-dimethylformamide mixture (AcOH + DMF) leads to the formation of corresponding sulphoxide. The reaction is first order each in Met, THexABC and [H⁺]. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The reaction rate have been determined at different percentage of AcOH + DMF mixtures at different temperatures and activation parameters calculated. The reaction does not induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Methionine, tetrahexylammonium bromochromate, kinetics, oxidation.

Introduction

Although all amino acids can be biologically oxidized, the sulphur containing amino acids cysteine and methionine are readily oxidized by reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) due to their sulphur-containing side chain, which has low formal oxidation potentials. Methionine sulfoxide is a major product of Met oxidation.

The oxidation of methionine by different oxidants have been the subject of study by various workers due to its biological importance. Various oxidizing agents are used such as tetraethylammonium chlorochromate¹, benzimidazolium fluorochromate², chromic acid³, pyridinium fluorochromate⁴, pyridinium chlorochromate⁵, pyridinium bromochromate⁶, pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide⁷, benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate⁸, oxochromium(V) cations⁹, imidazolium fluorochromate¹⁰, quinolinium fluorochromate¹¹, quinolinium chlorochromate¹², chromium(VI): EDTA¹³ and many other well-known oxidizing agents.

Chromium compounds have been used in aqueous and non-aqueous medium for the oxidation of a variety of

organic compounds. Chromium compounds especially Cr^{VI} reagents have been versatile reagents and capable of oxidizing almost all the oxidisable organic functional groups¹⁴. The development of newer chromium(VI) reagents for the oxidation of organic substrates continues to be of interest.

In recent years, a number of chromium(VI) containing compounds like tri/tetraalkylammonium halochromates have been used as oxidant for the oxidation of various organic substrates. Some of the new alkylammonium halochromates like tetraethylammonium bromochromate¹⁵, tributylammonium chlorochromate¹⁶, tripropylammonium fluorochromate¹⁷, tetrabutylammonium fluorochromate¹⁸, trialkylammonium fluorochromates¹⁹, teraalkylammonium bromochromates²⁰ and triethylammonium chlorochromate²¹ have been used to study the kinetics of oxidation of various organic compounds.

Organic chemists must often choose from hundreds of oxidizing agents and reaction conditions to perform a desired oxidation without affecting other functional groups present or causing side reactions. Although there are a broad variety of oxidants derived from Cr^{VI} reported in

literature to perform oxidation reactions the easy access to the THexABC²⁰ and the high yields reported in the literature prompted us to select this reagent for our study. This reagent is mild and efficient for kinetic study.

As a part of our continuing work towards the oxidation of methionine^{1,2}, we report here, the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of methionine by THexABC in various percentage of AcOH + DMF mixture, with the view to understand the utility of solvent variation studies in the understanding of the mechanism of this biologically important amino acid, because it may reveal the mechanism of amino acid metabolism.

Materials and methods :

Reagents : Tetrahexylammoniumbromide and chromium trioxide were obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). DL-Methionine (E. Merck, Germany) was used as received. Acetic acid was purified by standard method and the fraction distilling at 118 °C was collected. *p*-Toluene sulfonic acid (*p*-TsOH) is used as the source of hydrogen ion.

Synthesis of tetrahexylammonium bromochromate(VI), $(C_6H_{13})_4N[CrO_3Br]$:

Tetrahexylammonium bromochromate(VI), was prepared by the reported method²⁰ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. Chromium(VI) oxide (1.0 g, 10 mmol) was dissolved in dry acetonitrile (25 ml) in a beaker with at 0 °C. To the resultant clear orange solution, tetrahexylammonium bromide (4.34 g, 10 mmol) was added under stirring at room temperature. Within 1 h, a clear orange solution formed which upon refrigerating gave solid THexABC. The resulting product was isolated by filtration. The solid was washed with hexane, ether and dried under vacuum for 1 h. m.p. 90–92 °C (Reported 90 °C) (Found : C, 53.94; H, 9.80; N, 2.70. Caclcd. for $C_{24}H_{52}BrCrNO_3$: C, 53.93; H, 9.73; N, 2.62%).

Experimental

Kinetic measurements : Reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of Met ($\times 15$ or more) over THexABC. The solvent was 40% AcOH + 60% DMF, unless mentioned otherwise. The studies were carried out in the temperature range of 298–313 K and were followed upto 80% completion by monitoring the decrease in [THexABC] at 352 nm spectrophotometrically using Shimadzu UV-1800 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} were computed from linear ($r > 0.990$) least-square plots of $\log [THexABC]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants k_2 were computed from the relation $k_2 = k_{obs}/[Met]$.

Data analysis : Data analysis were performed using Microcal Origin (version 6.0) computer software. The goodness of the fit is discussed using the correlation coefficients and standard deviations.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by performing the several sets of experiments with varying amounts of THexABC largely in excess over methionine. The disappearance of THexABC was monitored until constant titre values were obtained.

The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for a few hours. Then, sodium bicarbonate was added and stirred vigorously, followed by drop wise addition of benzoyl chloride solution. The precipitate *N*-benzoyl methionine sulphoxide was confirmed by its m.p. 183 °C. The procedure is similar to the one employed in the oxidation of L-methionine by chromium(VI). Acetone-ethanol mixture (1 : 1) added to the reaction mixture resulted in the precipitate of methionine sulphoxide¹, which was identified by its m.p. 238 °C. The yield of sulphoxide was 89%.

Effect of varying THexABC concentration : The concentration of THexABC was varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-3} to 3.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻¹ at constant [Met], [H⁺] at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The near

Table 1. Effect of varying the concentration of [Met], [THexABC] and [H⁺] on the rate of reaction at 303 K

10 ³ [THexABC] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ² [Met] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	3.0	0.4	8.56
1.5	3.0	0.4	8.52
2.0	3.0	0.4	8.66
2.5	3.0	0.4	8.48
3.0	3.0	0.4	8.72
2.0	1.0	0.4	2.78
2.0	2.0	0.4	5.60
2.0	4.0	0.4	11.38
2.0	5.0	0.4	14.30
2.0	6.0	0.4	17.44
2.0	3.0	0.1	2.08
2.0	3.0	0.2	4.22
2.0	3.0	0.3	6.34
2.0	3.0	0.5	10.72
2.0	3.0	0.6	13.00
2.0	3.0	0.4	8.58 ^a

^aContained 0.003 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Solvent composition : 40% Acetic acid : 60% DMF.

constancy in the value of k_{obs} irrespective of the concentration confirms the first order dependence on THexABC.

Effect of varying Met concentration : The concentration of methionine was varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-2} to 6.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻¹ at 303 K and keeping all other reactant concentrations as constant and the rates were measured (Table 1). The rate of oxidation increased progressively on increasing the concentration of methionine. The plot of log k_1 versus log [Met] gave the slope of 1.02 ($r = 0.997$). Under pseudo-first order conditions, the plot of $1/k_1$ versus $1/[Met]$ was linear with a negligible intercept indicating that the intermediate formed in a slow step got consumed in a subsequent fast step.

Effect of varying [H⁺] concentration : *p*-Toluene sulfonic acid has been used as a source of H⁺ in reaction medium. The concentration of H⁺ was varied in the range 0.1 to 0.6 mol dm⁻¹ keeping all other reactant concentration as constant at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The acid catalysed nature of this oxidation is confirmed by an increase in the rate on the addition of H⁺. The plot of log k_1 versus log [H⁺] is a straight line with the slope of 1.03 ($r = 0.999$). Therefore, order with

respect to H⁺ is one for methionine. THexABC may become protonated in the presence of acid. The protonated THexABC may function as an effective oxidant.

The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of THexABC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

The formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PFC⁴.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile : Vinyl monomers like acrylonitrile are added to the reaction mixture under nitrogen atmosphere to find out whether the reaction under investigation involves the formation of free radicals as the reaction intermediates. In the present study, freshly distilled acrylonitrile free from inhibitor is added to the reaction mixture containing 0.4 mol dm⁻¹ *p*-TsOH. After the completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture is diluted with methanol to observe the formation of polymer. It is observed that the oxidation reaction does not induce the polymerization (Table 1). Thus, a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals is unlikely.

Effect of varying ionic strength of reaction rate : The ionic strength of the reaction medium is changed by the addition of anhydrous sodium perchlorate and the influence of ionic strength on the reaction rate has been studied. The values of the rate constants at different ionic strength of the reaction medium has no significant effect on the reaction rate (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of ionic strength on the oxidation of methionine at 303 K

10 ² [NaClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)
0.0	8.66
1.0	8.52
2.0	8.72
3.0	8.58
4.0	8.76
5.0	8.72

10² [Met] = 3.0 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [THexABC] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³;
10 [H⁺] = 4.0 mol dm⁻³.

Solvent composition = 40% AcOH-60% DMF (v/v).

Effect of solvent polarity on reaction rate : The influence of solvent on the rate of any reaction can be described in terms of solvation which is a stabilization process²². The oxidation of methionine has been studied in the binary mixture of acetic acid and DMF as the solvent medium. For the oxidation of methionine, the reaction rate increased remarkably with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent medium. These results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of varying solvent polarity on the rate of reaction of oxidation of methionine by THexABC at 303 K

%AcOH- DMF (v/v)	Dielectric constant	1/D	10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)			
			298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
0-100	38.30	0.0261	4.02	6.16	9.05	14.01
10-90	34.11	0.0293	4.40	6.60	9.80	15.15
20-80	30.19	0.0331	4.75	7.12	10.90	16.62
30-70	26.52	0.0377	5.13	7.72	11.80	17.72
40-60	23.08	0.0433	5.45	8.66	13.06	20.16
50-50	19.85	0.0504	6.44	10.00	15.20	22.80
60-40	16.80	0.0595	7.84	12.00	18.24	27.42
70-30	13.92	0.0718	9.66	14.60	23.08	33.60

10² [Met] = 3.0 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [THexABC] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 4.0 mol dm⁻³

The effect from solvent composition on the reaction rate was studied by varying the concentration of acetic acid from 0% to 70%. The pseudo-first order rate constants were estimated for the oxidation of methionine, with THexABC in the presence of *p*-TsOH at a constant ionic strength. The reaction rate increases markedly with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the medium (Table 3). When the acid content increases in the medium, the acidity of the medium is increased whereas the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased. These two effects cause the rate of the oxidation to increase markedly. The enhancement of the reaction rate with an increase in the amount of acetic acid generally may be attributed to two factors, viz. (i) the increase in acidity occurring at constant [H⁺] and (ii) the decrease in the dielectric constant with an increase in the acetic acid content.

The plot of log k₁ versus 1/D (dielectric constant) is linear with positive slope (Fig. 1) suggesting the presence of either dipole-dipole or ion-dipole type of interaction between the oxidant and the substrate²³. Plot of log k₁

Fig. 1. Plot of 1/D against log k₁ showing the effect of solvent polarity for the oxidation of methionine by THexABC.

versus $(D - 1)/(2D + 1)$ is a curvature indicating the absence of dipole-dipole interaction in the rate determining step. Positive slope of log k₁ versus 1/D plot indicates that the reaction involves a cation-dipole type of interaction in the rate determining step.

Amis (1967) holds the view that in an ion-dipole reaction involving a positive ionic reactant, the rate would decrease with increasing dielectric constant of the medium and if the reactant were to be a negatively charged ion, the rate would increase with the increasing dielectric constant. In this case there is a possibility of a positive ionic reactant, as the rate decreases with the increasing dielectric constant of the medium²³. Due to the polar nature of the solvent, transition state is stabilized, i.e. the polar solvent molecules surround the transition state and result in less disproportion.

Thermodynamic parameters : The kinetics of oxidation of methionine was studied at four different temperatures viz. 298, 303, 308 and 313 K. The second order rate constants were calculated. The Arrhenius plot of log k₂ versus 1/T is found to be linear (Fig. 2). From Arrhenius plot, the activation energy, E_a is calculated for different percentage of AcOH and DMF mixture and the values are given in Table 4. Eyring's plot of log (k₂/T) vs 1/T is given in Fig. 3. Various thermodynamic parameters like enthalpy of activation (ΔH[#]), entropy of activation (ΔS[#]) and free energy of activation (ΔG[#]) were calculated from k₂ at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least square and the values are

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plot for the oxidation of methionine by THexABC.

presented in Table 4. The entropy of activation is negative for methionine.

Isokinetic relationship : The reaction is neither isoenthalpic nor isoentropic but complies with the compensation law also known as the isokinetic relationship.

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H^\circ + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger \quad (4)$$

The isokinetic relationship is tested by plotting the logarithms of rate constants at two different temperatures ($T_2 > T_1$) against each other according to eq. (5).

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (5)$$

The linear relationship in Exner plots²⁴ at $4 + \log k_2$ (298 K) and $4 + \log k_2$ (303 K) observed in the present study imply the validity of the isokinetic relationship (Fig. 4). Isokinetic temperature obtained is 418 ± 12 K. The

Table 4. Activation parameters and second order rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by THexABC in AcOH-DMF mixture at different compositions

%AcOH-DMF	$10^4 \times k_2$ (s ⁻¹)				E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹) (at 303 K)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K				
0-100	1.34	2.05	3.02	4.70	64.1	73.1 ± 4.0	61.8 ± 1.3	84.0 ± 2.5
10-90	1.47	2.20	3.27	5.05	63.3	75.4 ± 2.8	60.9 ± 1.0	83.7 ± 1.8
20-80	1.58	2.37	3.63	5.54	65.1	70.1 ± 1.4	62.4 ± 0.5	83.6 ± 0.9
30-70	1.71	2.57	3.93	5.90	62.8	72.5 ± 1.7	61.7 ± 0.6	83.5 ± 1.2
40-60	1.81	2.88	4.35	6.72	67.4	60.7 ± 3.0	64.9 ± 1.0	83.3 ± 1.9
50-50	2.15	3.34	5.07	7.60	65.3	66.4 ± 0.6	62.8 ± 0.2	82.9 ± 0.4
60-40	2.61	4.00	6.08	9.14	64.2	66.3 ± 1.7	62.2 ± 0.6	82.3 ± 1.2
70-30	3.22	4.87	7.69	11.20	65.1	63.7 ± 2.8	62.4 ± 1.0	81.7 ± 1.8

10^2 [Met] = 3.0 mol dm⁻³ ; 10^3 [THexABC] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³ ; [H⁺] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³

Fig. 3. Eyring's plot for the oxidation of methionine by THexABC.

Fig. 4. Exner's plot of $4 + \log k_2$ (298 K) versus $4 + \log k_2$ (303 K) for the oxidation of methionine by THexABC.

linear isokinetic correlation implies that methionine is oxidized by the same mechanism at different percentage of AcOH and DMF mixture and the changes in the rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation²⁵.

Mechanism of oxidation : Based on the above kinetic observations, i.e. first order dependence on [Met], [THexABC] and [H⁺], the following mechanism is proposed (Scheme 1). Under the present experimental conditions, methionine is oxidized to the sulphoxide stage only. The linear increase in the rate with acidity suggests the involvement of protonated THexABC in the rate determining step. In the first step THexABC becomes protonated. The protonated THexABC attacks the substrate, in

a slow step, to form a complex, which subsequently decomposes to give the products in a fast step. The proposed scheme envisages an oxygen atom transfer from the oxidant and that is in agreement with the earlier observations. The electrophile attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N² reaction¹².

The above mechanism leads to the following rate law :

$$\text{Rate} = K [\text{Complex}]$$

$$[\text{Complex}] = K' [\text{Met}] [\text{THexABCH}^+]$$

$$[\text{THexABCH}^+] = k [\text{THexABC}][\text{H}^+]$$

$$[\text{Complex}] = KK'k [\text{Met}][\text{THexABC}][\text{H}^+]$$

$$-d[\text{THexABC}]/dt = KK'k [\text{Met}][\text{THexABC}][\text{H}^+]$$

The rate law in its final form accounts for the observed

Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of methionine by THexABC.

kinetics. The negative entropy of activation suggests complex formation in the transition state.

Comparison of oxidation of Met by THexABC with other chromium(VI) reagents :

It is of interest to compare the mode of oxidation of methionine by PFC⁴, PCC⁵, PBC⁶, IFC¹⁰, QCC¹² and chromium(VI) : EDTA¹³. The oxidation by PFC, PCC, PBC and THexABC exhibits second order kinetics; first order with respect to each reactant. Solvation model for the oxidation of methionine by IFC and QCC have been reported. Here also the oxidation by IFC and QCC exhibits first order kinetics with respect to each reactants. The oxidation by chromium(VI) : EDTA exhibits first order with respect to Cr^{VI} and a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to methionine.

Conclusion :

In this paper, kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of Met by THexABC in various percentage of AcOH and DMF is reported. The reaction is first order each in Met and THexABC. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. Under the employed experimental conditions, methionine is oxidized to the corresponding sulphoxide stage only. Various thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation have been reported. The entropy of oxidation is negative, suggesting the formation of a complex in the slow step. The lowering of dielectric constant of reaction medium increases the reaction rate significantly. The ionic strength of the reaction medium does not affect the rate of the oxidation. The reaction does not show the polymerization, which indicates the absence of free radical intermediate in the oxidation.

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References

1. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Arab. J. Chem.*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2011.01.031>.
2. S. S. Mansoor, S. S. Shafi and S. Z. Ahmed, *Arab. J.*

- Chem.*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2011.06.026>.
3. Zaheer Khan, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 350.
4. V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1996, 290.
5. V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 607.
6. V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 418.
7. V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 291.
8. M. Bhatt, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2001, **24**, 372.
9. N. S. Venkataramanan, S. Rajagopal and M. Vairamani, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2007, **101**, 274.
10. B. John, M. Pandeewaran, D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **71**, 19.
11. D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **73**, 735.
12. M. Pandeewaran, B. John, D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **70**, 145.
13. S. Meenakshisundaram and R. Vinothini, *Croatica Chemica Acta*, 2003, **76**, 75.
14. W. B. Wiberg, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1965.
15. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Zeitschrift für Physikalische Chemie.*, 2011, **225**, 249.
16. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Reac. Kinet. Mech. Cat.*, 2010, **100**, 21.
17. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2010, **155**, 85.
18. S. Ghammami and S. A. S. Sajadi, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **70**, 1243.
19. S. Ghammami, S. Khorsandtabar, A. Moghimi and H. Sahebalzamani, *J. Mex. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **53**, 41.
20. S. Ghammami, K. Mehrani, H. Afrand, Z. Javanshir, G. Rezaeibehbahani, A. Moghimi and Z. S. Aghbolagh, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **54**, 491.
21. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Arab. J. Chem.*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2010.11.004>.
22. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 69.
23. E. S. Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, New York, 1967, 42.
24. O. Exner, J. R. Streitwiser and R. W. Talt, "Progress in Physical Organic Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1973, 41.
25. J. F. Leffler and E. Grunwald, "Rates and Equilibrium of Organic Reactions", Wiley, New York, 1963.

